

EFFECT OF BIOFERTILIZERS (*Azotobacter* and *Azospirillum*) ALONE AND IN COMBINATION WITH REDUCED LEVELS OF NITROGEN ON POST HARVEST QUALITY OF CAULIFLOWER CV. SNOWBALL-16

P. B. Sable*

* Assistant Professor, Section of Horticulture, Shri Shivaji Agriculture College, Amravati, M. S. India, Pin – 444603.

pb_sable@rediffmail.com,

MS Received: 16.11.2024; MS Revised: 29.12.2024; MS Accepted: 30.12.2024)

MS 3356

(RESEARCH PAPER IN HORTICULTURE.)

Abstract

An experiment was conducted during rabi season of 2004-05 involving three levels of nitrogen (0, 100 and 75% nitrogen) with four levels of biofertilizers (no inoculation, *Azospirillum*, *Azotobacter* and *Azotobacter* + *Azospirillum*). Out of the twelve treatment combinations the best treatment was 75 per cent nitrogen (120 kg ha⁻¹) + *Azotobacter* + *Azospirillum* which showed significant increase in ascorbic acid content in curd (87.00 mg/100g), total nitrogen content in plant (2.98%), protein content in curds (18.62%) and compactness of curd (97.39%).

Keywords: Biofertilizers, Nitrogen levels, Quality and Cauliflower.

Introduction

Cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis* L.) is one of the most important winter vegetables among the cole crops. The current trend is of organic farming using organic fertilizers like biofertilizers of microbial origin with limited use of chemical fertilizers. Application of *Azospirillum* and *Azotobacter* inoculants in vegetable crops has been much significance because they not only fix atmospheric nitrogen but also produces growth promoting and antifungal substances. (Sharma *et al.*, 1986). Hence keeping in view these facts, the present investigation was undertaken to explore the effect of *Azotobacter* and *Azospirillum* with reduced levels of nitrogen on post harvest quality of Cauliflower.

Materials And Methods

The experiment was conducted at main farm, Department of Horticulture, Late Shri Vasantrao Naik Marathwada Agricultural University, Parbhani in Factorial Randomized Block Design (FRBD) with twelve treatment combinations having three replications. There were three levels of nitrogen i.e. 0, 100 and 75 per cent nitrogen (symbolized as N₀, N₁ and N₂ respectively) and four levels of biofertilizers i.e. no inoculation, *Azospirillum*, *Azotobacter* and *Azotobacter* + *Azospirillum* (symbolized as B₀, B₁, B₂ and B₃ respectively). Before transplanting seedlings were dipped in slurry of biofertilizers for 10 minutes. Uniform and healthy one month old seedlings of cauliflower Cv. Snowball-16 were transplanted in November with spacing of 60 cm x 45 cm. the plot had a gross area of 3.0 m x 2.7 m and net area of 2.4 m x 1.8 m. fertilizer dose applied was 160 kg N + 80 kg P₂O₅ + 80 kg K₂O ha⁻¹. Half dose of nitrogen was given according to treatment level i.e. 100 per cent and 75 per cent nitrogen in the recommended dose. Remaining half dose of nitrogen was given one month after transplanting i.e. at earthing up. FYM @ 10 tones ha⁻¹ was applied at field preparation. Observations on quality were recorded Ascorbic acid content in curd was estimated by using 2,6 dichloro phenol indophenols visual titration method (A.O.A.C., 1990) expressed in mg/100 g. Nitrogen content from plant sample was determined by Microkjeldhal's method as described by A.O.A.C. (1975). Protein content of curd was calculated from nitrogen content of curd multiplied by factor 6.25 to calculate total protein content of curd.

According to Pearson (1931) compactness of curd was determined by the formula $Z = \frac{C}{W^3} \times 100$ where Z is the index of compactness, C is the net weight of curd and W is the average of lateral and polar diameter of the curd. Higher value indicates more compactness of curd.

Results And Discussion**Effect on quality attributes :****Nitrogen effect :**

Data presented in Table 1 revealed that nitrogen application had significant effect on quality attributes of cauliflower. Quality attributes of cauliflower decreased as dose of nitrogen application reduced. Significantly maximum ascorbic acid content i.e. vitamin C in curd (73.99 mg/100 g), total nitrogen in the plant (2.64%), protein content in curd (16.51%) and compactness of curd (92.75%) were recorded in treatment N₁ (100 per cent nitrogen) i.e. plants receiving 160 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ as compared to 75 per cent nitrogen (N₂) and control (N₀).

The increase in vitamin C content might be due to growth promoting substances, which could have accelerated synthesis of carbohydrates resulting in increase in vitamin C content. The increase in compactness may be due to increased chlorophyll content in leaves and more number of inner leaves. These results are in close proximity with the findings Kamili *et al.* (2002) in brinjal, Khandait (1996) in cabbage and Bambal *et al.* (1998) in cauliflower.

Biofertilizer Effect:

Biofertilizers had a significant effect on quality attributes of cauliflower. Maximum ascorbic acid (83.68 mg/100 g) content of curd, total N content in plant (2.70 %), protein content of curd (16.91 %) and compactness index of curd (94.46%) were produced in treatment B₃ (*Azotobacter* + *Azospirillum*).

The increase in vitamin C content over rest of the treatments might be due to nutritional and stimulatory behavior of microbial inoculants. These findings are supported with the results of Bambal *et al.* (1998) in cauliflower and Bobade (2001) in cabbage.

Interaction effect:

It is revealed from data presented in Table 1 that interaction effect of nitrogen and biofertilizer was found significant.

The treatment combination consisting of N₂B₃ (75% N + *Azotobacter* + *Azospirillum*) recorded maximum ascorbic acid (87.00 mg / 100 g), total nitrogen content (2.98%) in the plant, protein content (18.62%) in curd and compactness of curd (97.39 %) over rest of the treatment combinations.

The increase in vitamin C content might be due to growth promoting substances, which could have accelerated synthesis of carbohydrates resulting in increase in vitamin C content.

The increased nitrogen uptake and better utilization of added manure and fertilizers by plants due to these bacteria may be one of the causes for increase in nitrogen content of plant.

The increase in compactness of curd may be due to increased chlorophyll content in leaves and more number of inner leaves. Ukey (1993) reported combined inoculation of *Azotobacter* and *Azospirillum* + 20 per cent reduction in N increased the quality attributes in cauliflower.

From the above investigation, it is concluded that treatment of *Azotobacter* + *Azospirillum* seedling inoculation with 75% of the recommended nitrogen dose were equally effective for getting maximum post harvest quality of cauliflower with that of recommended dose of nitrogenous fertilizer. Thus there is a saving of 25% nitrogen in getting maximum quality of cauliflower.

References

1. A.O.A.C. (1975) Official method of Analysis. Association of Official Analytical Chemists Ed. 12th Washington, D.C.
2. A.O.A.C. (1990) Official Method Of Analysis, Association of Official Analytical Chemists Ed. 15th Washington, D.C. 2007, 72 : 918-919.
3. Bambal, A. S. Verma, R. M., Panchabhai, D. M., Mahorkar, V. K. and Khankhane, R. N. (1998) Effect of biofertilizers and nitrogen levels on growth and yield of cauliflower. Orissa J. Hort., 26(2); 14-17.

4. **Bobade, P. M. (2001)**Effect of different levels of fertilizers and spacing on growth, yield and quality of cabbage. M.Sc.(Agri.) Thesis, Dr. P. D. K.V., Akola
5. **Kamili, I. A., Zargar, M. Y. and Chatoo, M. A. (2002)**Effect of Microbial inoculants, chemical nitrogen and their combination on Brinjal. Veg. Sci., 29(1): 87-89.
6. **Khandait, C.M. (1996)**.Effect of Azotobacter, Azospirillum alone and in combination with reduced doses of nitrogen on growth and yield of cabbage. M.Sc.(Agri.) Thesis, Dr. P.D.K.V., Akola.
7. **Sharma, S. K. (2002)**Effect of Azospirillum, Azotobacter and nitrogen on growth and yield of cabbage. Indian J. Agri. Sci., 79(2); 555-557.
8. **Ukey, R. N. (1993)** Effect of Azotobacter, Azospirillum alone and in combination with reduced does of nitrogen on growth and yield of **cauliflower** M.Sc.(Agri.) Thesis, Dr. P.D.K.V., Akola (M.S.).

Table Effect of different levels of nitrogen and biofertilizers on post harvest quality of cauliflower Cv. Snowball 16

Treatments	Ascorbic acid content in curd (mg/100 g)	Protein content in curd (%)	Total nitrogen content in plant (%)	Compactness content of curd (%)
N ₀ B ₀ (control)	52.00	8.68	1.39	78.36
N ₁ B ₀	63.00	14.31	2.29	91.37
N ₂ B ₀	62.00	13.62	2.18	88.13
N ₀ B ₁	59.30	12.25	1.96	83.99
N ₁ B ₁	75.60	17.12	2.74	92.56
N ₂ B ₁	71.00	16.52	2.64	90.53
N ₀ B ₂	57.00	11.87	1.90	82.15
N ₁ B ₂	74.00	16.68	2.67	91.15
N ₂ B ₂	67.66	15.00	2.40	89.51
N ₀ B ₃	80.66	14.18	2.27	90.08
N ₁ B ₃	83.38	17.93	2.87	95.92
N ₂ B ₃	87.00	18.62	2.98	97.39
Nitrogen levels				
No	62.24	11.74	1.88	83.64
N ₁	73.99	16.51	2.64	92.75
N ₂	71.91	15.94	2.55	91.39
F Test	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig
SE ±	0.69	0.17	0.022	0.43
CD at 5%	2.02	0.50	0.066	1.27
Biofertilizers Levels				
B ₀	59.00	12.20	1.95	85.95
B ₁	68.63	15.29	2.44	89.02
B ₂	66.22	14.51	2.32	87.60
B ₃	83.68	16.91	2.70	94.46
F test	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig
SE ±	0.79	0.20	0.026	0.50
CD at 5%	2.34	0.58	0.077	1.46
Interaction (N x B)				
F test	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig
SE ±	1.38	0.34	0.045	0.86
CD at 5%	4.05	1.02	0.133	2.54